

IMPLEMENTATION OF ADAPTIVE-PID CONTROL IN A 10 L STIRRED TANK HEATER

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ABSTRACT

When operating a thermal reactor, the temperature of the reactor must be closely regulated to preserve its product specifications. Consequently, a control strategy needs to be developed. In order to address the problem of instability in reactor operation, a 10-liter stirred tank heater (STH) will be employed in the study's laboratory. To maintain a steady volume, the tank was made to overflow. A process reaction curve was employed for fine-tuning PID parameters. The XCOS software was chosen to examine the process control models. The tuning experiment produced controller gain $K_c = 215$ [kJ/(minute.K)], the integral time constant $\tau_I = 0.3$ minute, and the derivative time constant $\tau_D = 0.075$ minute. In this work, the two temperature control models of the conventional PID and the novel adaptive PID in a 10-liter stirred tank heater were proposed. The two control models with their tuning parameters provided quick and stable responses, as demonstrated in the dynamic simulation study. The integral of the absolute value of the error (IAE) at the tank outlet temperature for conventional control and adaptive control is 1.76 and 0.55 oC, respectively. The adaptive PID controller performed admirably and responded better than conventional PID, according to the closed-loop dynamic simulation.

Keywords: Adaptive; Closed-loop; Open-loop; PID; PRC; STH; XCOS

INTRODUCTION

Reactor technologies, such as continuous stirred tank reactors (CSTR) equipped with coil or jacket heaters, are frequently used in chemical process industries. On the other hand, the homogeneity of the fluid in a reactor has a major impact on its performance (Fogler, 2018). In the stirred tank heater (STH) process, temperature is one of the important parameters that needs to be kept constant at the desired value (set point). In this process, it is possible to change the temperature due to the mass or thermal disturbances that flow into the tank. To avoid changes in temperature that will affect the output of the tank, a temperature control system is needed so that the temperature is in accordance with the desired conditions. PID (proportional integral derivative) control is a well-known control method and is often used in the chemical process industries. However, the PID control parameters (proportional gain K_c , integral time constant τ_I , and derivative time constant τ_D) need to be properly set in order to generate quick and stable responses. The PID parameters must be able to react well in order to counter mass or thermal disruptions. This motivates us to approach the problem using a laboratory open-loop stirred tank heater (STH) experiment and a computer-based closed-loop simulation. Examining and comparing the two control methods of conventional PID and adaptive PID will be done.

Hermawan (2011) has implemented a conventional PID to regulate the temperature in a 10-liter STH. He adjusted the PID parameters using the process reaction curve (PRC). Hermawan and Haryono (2012) also used PRC for tuning PID parameters and conventional PID for controlling composition in a 10-liter mixing tank. Ruzianto et al. (2017) set the PID parameters of a heating system with automatic water mixing

using the trial-and-error method. Hermawan and Puspitasari (2018) have utilized the open-loop on-off method for tuning the PID composition control parameters in a 10-liter mixing tank. Hermawan and Puspitasari (2018) claimed that the relay-feedback-test approach can be replaced with the open-loop on-off method since it is straightforward and affordable. In 2020, Kristanto and Hermawan implemented the combined cascade-PI control in the Heater-PFR series; the cascade control improved the performance of the system.

The PID controller continuously measures the error between the setpoint and the measured value. Adaptive PID controllers perform better than conventional PID controllers in circumstances where input parameter fluctuations occur (Luyben and Luyben, 1997). Naba (2010) created an adaptive control mechanism to enhance system performance. Naba proposed the function evaluation to reduce the discrepancy between the actual plant conditions and the planned conditions. Darajat and Istiqphara (2021) implemented adaptive PI to regulate the water level in two interconnected tanks. The tank system can adapt to parameter changes that arise so that the tank filling process remains well controlled by using an adaptive PI control system. In 2021, Kanthalakshmi also used adaptive control to maintain liquid levels in the cone tank system. Tunjung et al. (2021) studied the use of a fuzzy-adaptive PID controller to regulate the temperature and liquid level in stirred tank heaters. Additionally, Madu et al. (2021) talked about how to construct a mixing tank control system utilizing the MIT Rule and the Model Reference Adaptive Control (MRAC) approach. Madu et al. (2021) used MATLAB 18.0 SIMULINK to simulate the model. Pham and Nguyen (2022) proposed adaptive fuzzy proportional integral sliding mode control (AFPISM) as a means of maintaining liquid level in two interconnected tank systems.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the process dynamics of a 10-liter STH and tune the PID parameters experimentally in a laboratory. The two temperature control methods of conventional PID and the new adaptive PID would be proposed. We created a STH in the laboratory with a 10-liter capacity to meet the objectives of this study. Laboratory experiments were conducted for the purpose of obtaining steady-state and PID parameters. The input disturbance to the fluid flowrate entering the tank was made based on the step function. XCOS was used to conduct both steady-state and dynamic simulations. The PID parameters and the robustness of both control methods were examined through rigorous closed-loop simulation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The experimental apparatus setup of the stirred tank heater (STH) is shown in Figure 1. Tank No. 1 in Figure 1 represents the STH. Stream 1 is a water stream with a flowrate $f(t)$ in L/minute and a temperature $T_1(t)$ in °C. Stream 2 is a heated water stream with a flowrate equal to $f(t)$ in L/minute and a temperature of $T_2(t)$ in °C. The tank was designed to overflow to maintain liquid volume V (L).

Pump dimmer No. 13 in Figure 1 can be used to change the flowrate $f(t)$. While flow sensor No. 8 is used to measure the flowrate $f(t)$. The flowrate is then displayed on LCD No. 10. Thermocouples No. 5a and 5b are used to measure the inlet and outlet temperatures of T_1 and T_2 , respectively. The measured temperatures can then be read on LCD No. 6 and recorded on laptop No. 7.

Open-loop experiments in the lab and closed-loop simulations using the XCOS program will be carried out to complete this work. To achieve the desired results, this task must be accomplished through the stages listed below:

Notes:

- | | | |
|------------------------|--------------------|----------------------|
| 1: Stirred Tank Heater | 6: Temperature LCD | 11: Storage tank |
| 2: Stirrer | 7: Laptop | 12: Submersible pump |
| 3: Electric heater | 8: Flow sensor | 13: Pump dimmer |
| 4: Watt regulator | 9: Solenoid valve | 14: Kickback valve |
| 5: Thermocouple | 10: Flow LCD | |

Figure 1. Experimental apparatus setup: stirred tank heater**2.1. Open-loop Model of a Stirred Tank Heater**

The differential equation of the STH in the deviation term is as follows:

$$\tau_p \frac{\Gamma_2(t)}{dt} + \Gamma_2(t) = K_1 F(t) + K_2 \Gamma_1(t) + K_3 Q(t) \quad (1)$$

where the process time constant τ_p [minute], process gains $K_1 \left[\frac{(K)(\text{minute})}{L} \right]$, K_2 (dimensionless), and $K_3 \left[\frac{(K)(\text{minute})}{L} \right]$, are defined as follows:

$$\tau_p = \frac{V}{\bar{f}} \quad (2)$$

$$K_1 = \frac{\bar{T}_1 - \bar{T}_2}{\bar{f}} \quad (3)$$

$$K_2 = \frac{\bar{f}}{\bar{f}} \quad (4)$$

$$K_3 = \frac{1}{\bar{f} \rho c_p} \quad (5)$$

Deviation terms for volumetric flowrate $F(t)$, the tank inlet temperature $\Gamma_1(t)$, the tank outlet temperature $\Gamma_2(t)$, and heater energy $Q(t)$ are defined as follows:

$$F(t) = f(t) - \bar{f} \quad (6)$$

$$\Gamma_1(t) = T_1(t) - \bar{T}_1 \quad (7)$$

$$\Gamma_2(t) = T_2(t) - \bar{T}_2 \quad (8)$$

$$Q(t) = q(t) - \bar{q} \quad (9)$$

Where \bar{f} is the initial volumetric flowrate (L/minute), \bar{T}_1 and \bar{T}_2 are the initial inlet and outlet temperatures (K), respectively, and \bar{q} is the initial heater energy (kJ/minute). The Laplace transform of the STH is then written as follows:

$$\Gamma_2(s) = \frac{K_1}{(\tau_p s + 1)} F(s) + \frac{K_2}{(\tau_p s + 1)} \Gamma_1(s) + \frac{K_3}{(\tau_p s + 1)} Q(s) \quad (10)$$

The open loop block diagram of the STH is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The open-loop block diagram of the STH.

2.2. Conventional PID Model

In this work, tank outlet temperature T_2 would be maintained at its desired value by manipulating the heater energy q . The measurement tool $G_m(s)$ and the control valve $G_v(s)$ Laplace transformations are taken to be 1. The Laplace transform of PID controller is written as follows:

$$G_c(s) = K_c \left(1 + \frac{1}{\tau_i s} + \tau_D s \right) \quad (11)$$

where K_c is a controller gain ($\frac{kJ}{K \cdot \text{minute}}$), τ_i is an integral time constant (minute), and τ_D is a derivative time constant (minute). Figure 3 shows the conventional PID block diagram.

Figure 3. The conventional PID block diagram of the STH.

2.3. Adaptive PID Model

Adaptive control is one feature of advanced control strategies. The controller can alter the process parameters in accordance with different operating conditions in order to determine the best control efficiency for each change (Luyben and Luyben, 1997). The adaptive controller gain is shown in the following way:

$$K_c = K_{c0} (1 + |\varepsilon(t)| \alpha) \quad (12)$$

where K_{c0} is initial controller gain ($\frac{kJ}{K \cdot \text{minute}}$) obtained by PRC experiment in laboratory, α is parameter to switch between the conventional PID and adaptive PID according to the following conditional rules:

$$\alpha = \begin{cases} 0.00 & \text{if } |\varepsilon(t)| \leq 0.001 \\ 100 & \text{if } |\varepsilon(t)| > 0.001 \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

The error signal $\varepsilon(t)$, which is the difference between set-point and measurement, is:

$$\varepsilon(t) = T_2^{SP} - T_2(t) \quad (14)$$

where T_2^{SP} is the T_2 set-point ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and $T_2(t)$ is the T_2 measurement ($^{\circ}\text{C}$). The adaptive PID block diagram of the STH is illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The adaptive PID block diagram of the STH.

One type of adaptive control is the gain scheduling strategy, which is effective for controlling systems whose dynamics change based on the operating environment. Gain scheduling is frequently used in nonlinear system control when the relationship between the dynamics of the plant and the operating conditions is known (Fernandes et al., 2013).

The adaptive control approach employed in this study is based on the planned adaptive control scheme, in which the controller settings are programmed according to changes in the process characteristics. The controller's settings are updated in accordance with the preprogrammed adjustment schedule as the process' input and output variables change significantly.

In this study, it would be possible to increase or decrease the tank inlet flowrate in a single step. Every time a feeding strategy is altered, a disturbance enters the interface-level control loop. This disturbance may cause a loss of control, depending on the conditions under which it occurs and its amplitude. It is consequently challenging in practice to find a particular controller tuning that would satisfy the most precise adjustments. As a result, the adaptive controller is a viable alternative, and all that is needed is a technique for updating the control parameters as well as a detailed analysis of how the closed-loop process performs in various operating conditions.

2.4. Open-loop Experiment in Laboratory

Figure 5 shows the STH equipment series in a laboratory. The purposes of the open-loop experiment are to:

- Identify steady-state variables and parameters.
- Investigate the temperature-dynamic behavior of the STH due to a change in flowrate disturbances.
- Tune the PID parameters, such as K_c , τ_i , and τ_D .

In the temperature dynamics experiment, the tank outlet temperature (T_2) is investigated based on step input flowrate disturbances. The input flowrate can be adjusted by immediately increasing or decreasing the pump power. In Figure 1, dimmer No. 13 controls the pump power.

In the tuning PID experiment, the Process Reaction Curve (PRC) method is used for tuning PID parameters (K_c , τ_i , and τ_D). The PRC can be created by immediately increasing the power heater No. 4 in Figure 1, so that the heater energy increases immediately. The tank outlet temperature is then investigated using thermocouple No. 5b in Figure 1.

The PRC experiment's output is a sigmoidal response. The PRC response is approximated with the first-order plus dead-time (FOPDT) response. The following describes the PRC transfer function (G_{PRC}):

$$G_{\text{PRC}}(s) = \frac{K_{\text{PRC}} e^{-t_D s}}{t_p s + 1} \quad (15)$$

The PRC gain, K_{PRC} ($\frac{\text{K}\cdot\text{minute}}{\text{kJ}}$) is written as follows:

$$K_{\text{PRC}} = \frac{\Delta CV}{\Delta MV} \quad (16)$$

where ΔCV is the difference between the new steady state value and the initial value of the outlet temperature T_2 ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), ΔMV is the difference between the new value and the initial value of the heater energy ($\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{minute}}$), t_D is the dead time (minute), and t_p is the PRC time constant (minute). Proportional gain (K_c), integral time constant (τ_I), and derivative time constant (τ_D) are then determined with the following Ziegler-Nichols formula (Smith and Corripio, 1997):

$$K_c = \frac{1.2 t_p}{K t_D} \quad (17)$$

$$\tau_I = 2.0 t_D \quad (18)$$

$$\tau_D = 0.5 t_D \quad (19)$$

Figure 5. The STH equipment series in a laboratory.

2.5. Closed-loop Simulation in the XCOS Environment

The closed-loop simulation is conducted to examine the proposed temperature control methods and the resulting PID parameters. The XCOS is used to solve and simulate the models. Furthermore, the closed loop's dynamic behaviors in response to a change in the input flowrate disturbance will be explored in this section. The proposed temperature control methods are the conventional PID and the new adaptive PID (APID), as shown in Figures 3 and 4, respectively.

The proposed temperature control strategies and the resulting PID parameters are examined using a closed-loop simulation. The models are solved and simulated using the XCOS. This section will also examine the closed loop's dynamic behaviors in response to an alteration in the input flowrate disturbance. The conventional PID and the new adaptive PID (APID), as depicted in Figures 3 and 4, are the two proposed temperature control techniques.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. The Open-loop Experiment Results

The open-loop experiment in a lab produced the steady-state variables of the STH, which are shown in Table 1. The process time constants and gains are then determined using those parameters, as given in Table 2. According to Stephanopoulos (1984), the process is considered more sensitive to a change in the input disturbance; the smaller the value of the process time constant, the larger the value of the process gain. The process gains K_1 , K_2 , and K_3 are around -0.52, 1, and 0.048, respectively, as shown in Table 2, and the process time constant of the STH is found to be rather low at 1.58 minutes. As a result, this system is thought to be sensitive to changes in input disturbances.

Table 1. Steady-state variables of the STH

Steady-state variables	Value
Heater energy, \bar{q} (kJ/minute)	46.488
Water flowrate, \bar{f} (L/minute)	5
Tank inlet temperature, \bar{T}_1 (°C)	26.8
Tank outlet temperature, \bar{T}_2 (°C)	29.4
Water density, ρ (kg/L)	0.9962
Specific heat, C_p [kJ/(kg.K)]	4.1815
Liquid volume, V (L)	7.9

Table 2. Steady-state parameters of the STH

Steady-state parameter	Value
$K_1 \left(\frac{\text{K.minute}}{\text{L}} \right)$	-0.52
K_2 (dimensionless)	1
$K_3 \left(\frac{\text{K.minute}}{\text{kJ}} \right)$	0.048
τ (minute)	1.58

The open-loop model then employs the steady-state parameters, which are entered into the XCOS block diagram as illustrated in Figure 6. Palette CSCOPE is used to record and display the XCOS responses (Scilab, 2023; Vieira et al., 2018). Additionally, the digital data can be saved in Workspace, and its output is subsequently duplicated into the Excel program for additional editing.

Figure 6. The XCOS open-loop block diagram of the STH

Figure 7 displays the open-loop response of T_2 to a step increase or decrease in water flowrate (f). The disturbance load is changed by 40%, going from 5 L/minute to 7 L/minute or from 5 L/minute to 3 L/minute. By changing the water volumetric flowrate, the tank outlet temperature T_2 goes down or up. In a time of 7.9 minutes, the temperature T_2 reaches the new steady-state value of 28.4 °C or 30.4 °C.

Figure 7 also depicts the XCOS model's response as dashed and solid lines. The XCOS responses have the same tendency and are comparable to the laboratory responses, as illustrated in Figure 7. This suggests that the model is reliable and can be applied further for process control design and simulation.

3.2. Tuning experiment results

Since this procedure can be easily performed in a laboratory, the process reaction curve (PRC) was chosen for fine-tuning the PID settings. The PRC was created using the following techniques in a laboratory open-loop experiment:

- The heater energy q is immediately increased from 44.49 kJ/minute to 72.36 kJ/minute (Figure 8).
- The dynamic behavior of the tank outlet temperature T_2 is then investigated from time to time until its value achieves the new steady-state value (Figure 9).

Figure 7. The open-loop response of T_2 to a step increase and decrease in water flowrate (f).

Figure 8. Step increase in the manipulated variable (MV) of heater energy (q).

From Figures 8 and 9, we can easily calculate the PRC gain K_{PRC} , the PRC time constant t_p , and the PRC dead time t_D as follows:

$$K_{PRC} = \frac{\Delta CV}{\Delta MV} = \frac{1.3}{25.87} = 0.05 \left(\frac{\text{K}\cdot\text{minute}}{\text{kJ}} \right) \quad (20)$$

$$t_p = \frac{3}{2}(t_2 - t_1) = \frac{3}{2}(1.5 - 0.6) = 1.35 \text{ minutes} \quad (21)$$

$$t_D = t_2 - t_p = 1.5 - 1.35 = 0.15 \text{ minutes} \quad (22)$$

The following is the result of applying equations (17), (18), and (19):

$$K_c = 215 \left(\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{K}\cdot\text{minute}} \right)$$

$$\tau_I = 0.3 \text{ minutes}$$

$$\tau_D = 0.075 \text{ minutes}$$

(23)

(24)

(25)

Figure 9. The temperature T_2 (CV) response to a step increase in heater energy (MV).

3.3. Closed-loop Simulation results

Figures 10 and 11, respectively, display the closed-loop XCOS diagrams for the conventional PID and the adaptive PID (APID). To assess the controllers' parameters, a closed-loop simulation of the STH's process control is required. The closed-loop simulation's secondary objective is to evaluate how resilient the suggested process control strategies are to variations in the input disturbance.

Figure 10. The conventional PID XCOS diagram in the STH.

Figure 11. The adaptive PID XCOS diagram in the STH.

In this work, a 2-unit step increase or decrease in the water inlet flowrate (f) has been made. The closed-loop responses of both control strategies are shown in Figures 12 to 15.

3.3.1. The closed-loop responses to a 2-unit step increase in water flowrate (f)

The temperature T_2 first decreases when the water flowrate f increases by 2 L/minute, as shown in Figure 12, but it can later be returned to its set point of 29.4 °C. This occurs as a result of the heater energy rapidly increasing to a new stable value of 68.17 kJ/minute, as depicted in Figure 13.

Figure 12. The closed-loop response of T_2 to a 2-unit step increase in water flowrate (f).

Figure 13. The closed-loop response of q to a 2-unit step increase in water flowrate (f).

The solid line in Figures 12 and 13 illustrates how the adaptive PID (APID) responds better than the conventional PID. The APID parameters are changed in accordance with the preprogrammed adjustment schedule as the input and output variables of the process change significantly (Fernandes et al., 2013). The operational environment affects the dynamics of the processes that the APID controls. The APID can modify the process parameters in accordance with diverse operating situations (Seborg et al., 2017).

3.3.2. The closed-loop responses to a 2-unit step decrease in water flowrate (f)

Figures 14 and 15 show the closed-loop responses of both control strategies to a step decrease in water flowrate f . When the water flowrate f drops by 2 L/minute, the temperature T_2 first rises and then returns to its initial temperature. This occurs because, as illustrated in Figure 15, the heater energy immediately decreases to a new steady value of 24.8 kJ/minute.

Figure 14. The closed-loop response of T_2 to a 2-unit step decrease in water flowrate (f).

Figure 15. The closed-loop response of q to a 2-unit step decrease in water flowrate (f).

Again, the solid line in Figures 14 and 15 illustrates how the adaptive PID responses outperform the conventional PID responses. The adaptive PID is able to update its parameters as input and output variables of the process change significantly.

3.3.3. The controller performance

The performance of both controllers would be compared under the same conditions of change. For example, performance can be assessed by calculating the integrals of the errors for responses in closed-loop following the application of load and set-point changes. Integral absolute error (IAE) is utilized in this study to compare PID and APID performances. The IAE is as follows:

$$IAE = \int_0^t |\varepsilon(t)| dt \quad (27)$$

IAE results for both controllers are listed in Table 3.

Table 3 shows that, compared to the conventional PID, the adaptive PID delivered lower values for the error integrals. Based on these findings, we can say that the gain scheduling adaptive PID beat the conventional PID in terms of controlling the STH process.

Table 3. Controllers' performance

Controller	IAE	
	Step increase f	Step decrease f
PID	1.76	1.76
APID	0.55	0.55

CONCLUSIONS

The 10-liter stirred tank heater open-loop experiment has been carried out successfully in the laboratory. At 1.58 minutes, the process time constant was discovered to be quite small. This shows that the process system was thought to be susceptible to a change in the input disturbance. The controller gain $K_c = 215$ [kJ/(K.minute)], the integral time constant $\tau_i = 0.3$ minute, and the derivative time constant $\tau_D = 0.075$ minute are the PID parameters that came out of the tuning experiment.

The conventional PID and the new adaptive PID methods have been proposed. The dynamic simulation investigation showed that the two control systems, with their tuning parameters, produced fast and stable responses. The integral of the absolute value of the error (IAE) at the tank outlet temperature is 1.76 °C for conventional control and 0.55 °C for adaptive control, respectively. The adaptive PID provided

lower values for the error integrals than the conventional PID. Based on these findings, we can say that the gain scheduling adaptive PID managed the STH operation better than the conventional PID.

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